

Mannich reaction of 3-hydroxycoumarin and 5,7-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin with secondary amines and 1-arylpiperazines

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The reaction of 3-hydroxycoumarin with 1-arylpiperazines and paraformaldehyde gives the corresponding 4-piperazinylmethyl derivatives. The reaction of 5,7-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin with secondary amines/1-arylpiperazines and paraformaldehyde gives the corresponding 6,8-bisaminomethyl derivatives.

The preparation of Mannich bases of coumarins took impetus from the fact a number of biologically active coumarins are widespread in nature¹ and α -pyrones have greater bioaccessibility than γ -pyrones². Less work has been done on the Mannich reaction on the α -pyrone part in coumarin. The 4-hydroxycoumarin under the Mannich condition gives mainly dicoumarol. Mannich bases of 3-hydroxycoumarins possess various biological activities³. In the group of

Mannich bases of dihydroxycoumarins, 8-aminomethyl-esculetins^{4,5}, 8-aminomethylrutins⁶ and 3-aminomethyl-4,8-dihydroxycoumarins⁷ are known. Due to high reactivity and the possibility of formation of positionally isomeric Mannich bases, dihydroxycoumarins are interesting substrates.

In the present investigation, the Mannich reaction of 3-hydroxycoumarin (1) and 5,7-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (2) was studied. The Mannich bases of 1 and 2 were also

prepared using 1-arylpiperazines (3) as the amine component.

3-Hydroxycoumarin (1) was reacted with 1-arylpiperazines (3) and paraformaldehyde to obtain 4-aminomethyl-3-hydroxycoumarins (4), where the reaction solely took place at the 4-position. The reaction of 5,7-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (2) with various secondary amines, including 3 and paraformaldehyde gave 6,8-bis(aminomethyl)-coumarins (5). It was observed that the reaction invariably gave bis-aminomethylation, irrespective of the molar ratio (2 : amine). This observation was strikingly different from that with esculetin derivative^{4,6}. It was also indicated that in 2, the 6- and 8-positions were equally reactive.

Experimental

The m.ps. were taken in open capillaries on a Campbell apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer and PMR spectra on a Varian T-60 spectrometer with TMS as the internal reference. The elemental analyses of the compounds were found to be satisfactory.

3-Hydroxycoumarin (1) was prepared from salicylaldehyde and *N*-acetylglycine following the reported procedure⁸: ν_{\max} 3370, 1690, 1405, 1250 cm^{-1} ; δ (DMSO- d_6) 7.1 (1H, s, C₄H), 7.3 (4H, m, ArH). 5,7-Dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (2) was prepared from phloroglucinol and ethyl acetoacetate following the reported procedure⁹: ν_{\max} 3450, 1675, 1620, 1600, 1390, 1370, 1300, 1150 cm^{-1} ; δ (DMSO- d_6) 2.5 (3H, s, 4-CH₃), 5.8 (1H, s, C₃H), 6.23 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, C₆H), 6.3 (1H, d, *J* 2 Hz, C₈H), 10.5 (1H, s, C₅-OH), 10.75 (1H, s, C₇-OH). 1-Arylpiperazines were prepared by the condensation of diethanolamine and anilines¹⁰.

4-(4-Aryl-1-piperazinylmethyl)-3-hydroxycoumarins (4): A solution of formalin (30% aq., 1.6 ml, 5 mmol) and 3 (5 mmol) in ethanol (20 ml) was stirred for 20 min and then 1 (5 mmol) was added to it. The solution was stirred for 2–3 h at room temperature and the separated solid was crystallized from ethanol: 4a (51%), m.p. 176–77°; b (37%), 166–67°; c (33%), 144–45°; d (60%), 180–81°; e (45%), 168–69°; f (51%), 170–71°; g (55%), 174–75, ν_{\max} 3410, 1720, 1630, 1450, 1300 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl₃) 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃),

2.96 (8H, b s, N(CH₂CH₂)₂N), 3.94 (2H, s, CH₂), 5.54 (1H, b s, OH), 7.72 (8H, m, ArH).

6,8-Bisaminomethyl-5,7-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarins (5): These compounds were prepared from 2 following the procedure given for 4 using mole ratio of 2 : amine as 1 : 2.2 and reaction time 4–5 h. The products were crystallized from ethanol: 5a (81%), m.p. 206–7°, ν_{\max} 3460, 1730, 1620, 1580, 1100 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl₃) 2.6 (12H, m, N(CH₂)₂ and 2×CH₂), 3.8 (11H, m, O(CH₂)₂ and 4-CH₃), 5.8 (1H, s, C₃-H); b (78%), 278–80°; c (79%), 238–40°, d (74%), 230–32°; e (71%), 152–53°; f (74%), 176–77°; g (68%), 152–153°; h (64%), 145–46°; i (78%), 167–68°; j (79%), 163–64°; k (70%), 158–59°; l (76%), 138–39°, ν_{\max} 3480, 1730, 1580, 1450, 1350, 1130 cm^{-1} , δ (CDCl₃) 2.28 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.58 (3H, s, 4-CH₃), 3.85–4.0 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.85 (8H, m, N(CH₂CH₂)₂N), 3.2 (8H, m, N(CH₂CH₂)₂N), 6.7–7.3 (8H, q, ArH).

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